

Discussion #1 about SIR Model: Introducing Spatial Aspect

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1 SIR model

Set of ordinary differential equations, as the basis of almost all other disease models [1], is the simple SIR (suceptible-infeceted-recoverd) model [2], which can be presented in the forms of

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -\frac{1}{N} aSI, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \frac{1}{N} aSI - bI, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = bI, \quad (3)$$

where S , I , and R are number of suceptible, infected, and recover, respectively. Equations (1) – (3) can also be presented in normalized forms [3]. Number of individuals in the population is assumed to be constant

$$N = S + I + R. \quad (4)$$

Parameters a is the infection rate, while b is the recover rate, that can be used to create another parameter

$$R_0 = \frac{a}{b}, \quad (5)$$

which will determine the final state of the system in the term of S , I , and R values.

2 Solution

Equations (1) – (3) will have exact solution in the form of [4]

$$t - t_0 = \int_{u_0}^u \frac{Nd\xi}{\xi(x_0 a \xi - aN - bN \ln \xi)}, \quad (6)$$

where t_0 is an arbitrary integration constant, which can be chosen that $t_0 = 0$, and u is a parameter. With the help of u , solution of S , I , and R can be obtained in the parametric forms

$$S(u) = x_0 u \quad (7)$$

$$I(u) = \frac{bN}{a} \ln u - x_0 u + N \quad (8)$$

and

$$R(u) = -\frac{bN}{a} \ln u. \quad (9)$$

Immediate addition of Equations (7) – (9) will give a constant number of individuals in the population N . Equation (6) shows that $u = u(t)$, then with Equations (7) – (9) it can be obtained that $S = S(t)$, $I = I(t)$, and $R = R(t)$ as expected.

There is also another way to get the solution of Equations (1) – (3), which is a numerical solution using a forward finite difference

$$f(t + \Delta t) = f(t) + \frac{df}{dt} \Delta t, \quad (10)$$

which gives

$$S(t + \Delta t) = S(t) - \frac{a}{N} S(t)I(t)\Delta t, \quad (11)$$

$$I(t + \Delta t) = I(t) + \frac{a}{N} S(t)I(t)\Delta t - bI(t)\Delta t, \quad (12)$$

$$R(t + \Delta t) = R(t) + bI(t)\Delta t, \quad (13)$$

where immediate addition of Equations (11) – (13) will produce

$$S(t + \Delta t) + I(t + \Delta t) + R(t + \Delta t) = S(t) + I(t) + R(t), \quad (14)$$

that also assures a constant population.

Figure 1. Result for $N = 100$, $S(0) = 99$, $I(0) = 1$, with $a = 0.25$, $b = 0.1$ (left column) and $a = b = 0.25$ (right column) as shown in [5] (top row) and this work with $\Delta t = 1$ (bottom row).

Figure 2. Times series of S , I , and R for $\Delta t: 1$ (top row), 5 (middle row), and 10 (bottom row).

Using the value of $\Delta t = 1$ we can get similar results [5] as shown in Figure 1 and influence of value Δt to the time series of S , I , and R are given in Figure 2. For given value of a and b if $\Delta t > 10$ the results are unlogical since one of the time series could be have negative values. From this we will use only $\Delta t = 1$. Increasing value Δt of also shift the peak of I to the right.

Table 1. Unlogical value of I_{\min} with the variation of Δt and N .

N	Δt	I_{\min}
100	11	-2.19E-01
200	11	1.93E-21
200	31	-4.65E-04
300	31	5.66E-70
300	47	-1.23E-06
400	47	-7.92E-01
416	47	-9.04E-01

Another way of avoiding this problem is by using larger number of population, but not all attempts are successfull as shown in Table 1. Values of I_{\min} printed in red is fo negative values, which should be zero instead of negative.

3 Spatial aspect with unconnected regions: Case of two regions

The SIR model can be advanced to include the spatial aspects, e.g. individual contact and population mobility [6], where in Equations (1) – (3) these aspects can only be included through the parameters a and b . In this part two unconnected regions are simulated simultaneously using parameter in Figure 1 (a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2) and for the whole region the parameters must be determined (a_T, b_T).

Figure 3. Time series of S (green), I (red), R (blue) for region 1 ($a_1 = 0.25, b_1 = 0.1$), region 2 ($a_2 = 0.25, b_2 = 0.25$), and the whole region, where region 1 (top row) for endemic case, region 2 (middle row) for non-endemic case, and the whole region (bottom row).

In this case $N_1 = N_2 = 100$ that makes $N_T = N_1 + N_2 = 200$. If we have only data of S_T, I_T , and R_T (Figure 3 bottom row), it is interesting how to obtained the data of each region even we can not perform the sampling. Before we discuss about that, the first thing to do is to obtained a_T and b_T from Figure 3 (bottom row) so that Equations (11) – (13) can produce the similar results. Since $a_1 = a_2 = 0.25$, the difference between the endemic and non-endemic case lies in the value of b_1

and b_2 . We can first assume that $a_T = a_1 = a_2$ and then try to vary b_T from b_1 to b_2 in order to get the suitable value. Some results for difference value of b_T are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Time series of S (green), I (red), R (blue) for the whole region as sum of two region (marked) and direct from SIR model (solid line) with $N = 200$, $I_T(0) = 2$, $a_T = 0.25$ and different values of b_T : 0.1 (first row), 0.15 (second row), 0.2 (third row), 0.25 (fourth row), and 0.185 (last row).

Varying manually value of b_T it can be obtained that $b_T = 0.185$ gives the best result as shown in last row of Figure 4. At least after about three months the results are the same for SIR model for the whole region and as summation of the two regions. Further step is to vary value of a_T in order to get better results, which is shown in Figure 5. It can be seen from the figure that $b_T = 0.25$ give good result after about three months, $b_T = 0.27$ is good for R before two months, then $b_T = 0.28$ suitable for S less than five weeks, and finally $b_T = 0.31$ is fitted for I less than a month. These tell us that it is not easy to get the right values of a_T and b_T that fit for all time since the data is summation of two regions with different a and b .

This case of two regions shows that even if the infection do obey the SIR model, but we only get the aggregate data for wider region while the infectious process only happens in the certain region with different characteristics, e.g. different value of a_T and b_T , the model for the whole region will be difficult and could mislead the interpretation of the results.

Different scenarios and more than one spatial level should be considered to assure that the model represents the system that we are discussing.

Figure 5. Time series of S (green), I (red), R (blue) for the whole region as sum of two region (marked) and direct from SIR model (solid line) with $N = 200$, $I_T(0) = 2$, $b_T = 0.185$ and different values of a_T : 0.25 (first row), 0.27 (second row), 0.28 (third row), and 0.31 (last row).

The schematic interaction between S , I , R compartments and also the two regions is given in Figure 6, where there is no interaction or connection between the two region.

Figure 6. Two unconnected regions with different value of N , a , b (left) is tested to be represented by one composite region specified by N_T , a_T and b_T .

For the next discussion following model, shown in Figure 7, is proposed that will take into account the interaction between S, I, R on both region through mobility, e.g. commuting, bussiness trip, etc.

Figure 7. Two connected regions with different value of N, a, b (left) is proposed to be represented by one composite region specified by N_T, a_T and b_T .

The question mark in Figure 7 stands for how is the parameters between region should be defined and what is the reason it should be that way. Isolation of a region or a lockdown will set these parameters to zero.

Summaries

From this discussion it can be summarized that the results from SIR model for aggregate data should be carefully interpreted due since the relation between summation of two regions and the whole regions is not linear, even when all of them obey the SIR model.

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